

Final report VMG: Synergy products for quantification of ABL stratification

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Introduction and Motivation

Profile observations of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) are essential for characterising its structure and evolution, as well as for better understanding the processes that take place within it. While in situ observations usually provide more resolved vertical measurements, their temporal resolution is generally low, making it difficult to elucidate the hourly varying ABL features that evolve with the diurnal cycle. To overcome this issue, ground-based remote sensing has been proven to be highly useful and remote sensing stations coverage has also significantly increased in the last decade. Different quantities obtained by ground-based remote sensing provide insights on ABL dynamics and have been increasingly applied to retrieve advanced information that is valuable for the characterization of layer heights (Kotthaus et al. 2023) and atmospheric stratification.

While the implementation of higher-order statistics of dynamic velocity variables reveals the diurnal evolution of the ABL and identifies turbulence sources (Manninen et al. 2018) the combination of multiple data products from different instruments has a great potential for elucidating different processes on it. For example, the characterization of ABL stratification based on a combination of data products obtained from different sensor types does have great potential, as demonstrated e.g. for the synergy between Microwave Radiometer (MWR), cloud radar and ALC observations for the improved physically consistent atmospheric profiles of temperature, absolute humidity, liquid water content (e.g. Löhnert et al. 2007; Ebell et al. 2017, Bell et al. 2022). Additionally, ABL height monitoring can be improved through synergistic implementations (Kotthaus et al. 2023, Saeed et al. 2016). ABL height detection was performed using a combination of several remote sensing instruments (MWR, DWL, Raman lidar) and validation against radiosondes showed good agreement at two stations on the Swiss plateau (Collaud et al. 2014). Further investigations have been performed over the last decade, comparing ABL height retrieval techniques based on remote sensing observations and radiosonde measurements, respectively (Seidel et al. 2010, Beyrich et al. 2012, Bianco et al. 2022). Many of these studies have found good correlations between remote sensing analyses in different weather conditions.

Here we investigate the capabilities and limitations of combining information from DWL and MWR to derive the synergistic product of the bulk Richardson number, *Rib*. Results are compared to *Rib* products calculated from in situ

radiosonde data and against the boundary layer classification method of Manninen et al (2018). To assess the implications of measurement uncertainties from the two sensor types, the thermal and dynamic components of the *Rib* are investigated regarding their importance for the description of atmospheric stability.

Site and dataset

The study is using observations conducted at the Jülich Observatory for Cloud Evolution (JOYCE). JOYCE is located at the Forschungszentrum Jülich in western Germany, at 111 m above mean sea level and constitutes an ACTRIS Cloud remote Sensing Station. The topography around is mostly flat with surroundings characterised by farming, and with open-cast coal mining areas with major power plants. Towards the southwest, around 15 km away from JOYCE, there are forested small hills (<500 m); additionally there is a forested 200-m-high mine pile about 3 km away. The climate in Jülich is temperate and humid with monthly average temperatures between 3.1°C in January and 18.1°C in July (Löhnert et al. 2015).

At JOYCE, continuous measurements of thermal and humidity profiles are performed from a MWR that is the Humidity and Temperature Profiler (HATPRO) (RPG, Meckenheim, Germany). This instrument is a Generation 5 MWR and operates within the K-band and V-band spectra (which is 22-32 GHz in the water and 51-58 GHz oxygen absorption lines). A retrieval model algorithm is utilised to derive the temperature and humidity profiles and radiosonde data is utilised as input in the forward model (Böck, et al. 2024). As a result, temperature and humidity measurements every 15 minutes and with a variable vertical resolution. The MWR starts measuring at its location at 0 m and its vertical resolution is 50 m close to the ground and coarser as elevation increases, for example at 2 km, the vertical resolution is 200 m and it continues to be lower upper in the atmosphere. Additionally, a DWL Streamline XR from HALO Photonics operates at JOYCE. This DWL emits a laser beam and by analysing the Doppler shift from the backscattered light it provides the wind speed along the beam. A combination of several beams can scan in different modes (DBS, VA, RHI) and allows the estimation of the three components of the wind vector. In the present VMG, we utilise velocity components as in the boundary layer classification (Manninen et al. 2018) that have a temporal resolution of 15 minutes and a vertical resolution of 25 m. Additionally, radiosonde observations at JOYCE on two summer days (5th of July and 21st of August 2022) are analysed with 3 radiosonde launches per day from 1100 UTC to 1400 UTC.

Methods

The bulk Richardson number (*Rib*) is estimated, similarly to previous investigations (Vickers et al 2004, Seibert et al 2002, Nguyen et al 2023), i.e., utilising the equation:

$$Rib = \frac{g}{\theta_0} \frac{(\theta_z - \theta_0)z}{u^2 + v^2}, \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where θ_0 and θ_z are the potential temperatures at the ground and at each height z respectively, u and v are the horizontal velocities at the same heights and g is

the acceleration of gravity. For the synergy analysis of remote sensing data is utilised, potential temperature data are derived from MWR air temperature, utilising $\theta = T\left(\frac{p_0}{p}\right)^{R/Cp}$, where $R/Cp = 0.286$ is the gas constant of air divided by the specific heat capacity at constant pressure and $p_0 = 1006 \text{ hPa}$ is the surface pressure. To combine this temperature profile with horizontal wind speed data observed with the DWL a common grid was defined with resolution of half an hour and 100 m. The ABL height estimated via the *Rib* thresholding technique requires the consideration of a critical bulk Richardson number *Ribc*. According to previous authors (Mahrt et al 2004, Zhang et al 2014) $Ribc = 0.25$ and $Ribc = 0.5$ are reasonable values for the threshold in *Rib* that should be considered for ABL height estimation. In the present study, both thresholds were tested and no significant difference was found, hence, we utilised $Ribc = 0.5$ to estimate an ABL height based on the *Rib*, that corresponds to the black line in both plots of figure 1.

DWL measurements provide sufficient temporal and spatial resolution for observing turbulent mixing in the ABL (e.g. Manninen et al. 2018). In the daytime convective boundary layer, convective mixing is largely driven by buoyancy production, which Manninen et al. (2018) identify automatically (red area in lower panels of figure 1), also allowing for the height of this convective layer to be derived from the vertical profile of eddy dissipation rate (ε) of turbulent kinetic energy, which is calculated from vertically pointing data:

$$\varepsilon = 2\pi\left(\frac{2}{3a}\right)^{3/2}\sigma_w^3\left(L^{2/3} - L_1^{2/3}\right)^{-3/2} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

where L_1 corresponds to the length scale of the scattering volume, L stands for the length scale of the largest eddies; $a = 0.55$ is the Kolmogorov constant for 1-dimensional wind spectra and σ_w is the standard deviation of the vertical velocity. Turbulence identification is derived from a threshold of ε , when $\varepsilon > 10^{-5} \text{ m/s}$ (Manninen et al 2018). The ABL classification operates in all weather conditions with high temporal (3 minutes) and vertical (30 m) resolutions; it contains only dynamical (DWL) data but provides very robust products that are compared with the synergistic variables in the present study.

Results

Evaluation of *Rib* synergy to estimate ABL height

As figure 1 shows, a clear diurnal cycle is elucidated by the *Rib*, with the unstable boundary layer growing in height during the morning phase and decaying in the afternoon. The ABL height (black contour) obtained from the *Rib* analysis and the convective boundary layer height determined from the eddy dissipation rate (magenta line) show a similar diurnal cycle. The ABL classification from DWL data (lower panels of figure 1) reveals an evolution of the convective region with a diurnal cycle similar to the one determined by *Rib*. At night, the *Rib* has positive

values, i.e. indicating stable conditions which is consistent with the non-turbulent ABL classification derived from DWL data.

While there is a general agreement between the ABL heights derived by *Rib* threshold methodology and the convective boundary layer height estimated via the analysis of the dissipation rate, some differences are also detected. The most evident feature is that there is a deeper development of turbulence in the ABL derived from the turbulent dissipation rate, using only DWL data. In order to assess those differences we analyse two example days in summer. During the morning phase after the sunrise, the unstable levels in the ABL increase with height, creating a growing ABL height. After the morning growing phase, there is another phase in which the ABL height remains relatively constant, at that time the convective ABL height is around 300 m higher than the *Rib* one for the 5th of July 2022 and it is approximately the same during the 21st of August 2022. However, in the afternoon decaying phase we notice that the convective height decays more rapidly than the *Rib* unstable values on both days. This behaviour elucidates that convective plumes cease as soon as solar radiation becomes weaker, whereas the thermal inertia causes that instability in a more comprehensive way (considering also thermal information) has a slower decayment around sunset. This temporal shift between convection and thermal decayment elucidates an added value of utilising *Rib* as a synergistic approach in the present VMG, because it actually monitors thermal instability in the ABL that is not necessarily always coincident with the purely dynamic part. Furthermore, another added value from the synergistic *Rib* can be derived from figure 1: there are some nighttime estimations of an ABL height via synergistic *Rib*, whereas purely dynamic retrievals are not able to capture nighttime ABL heights. After the afternoon decayment, convection ceases and the boundary layer classification does not provide any height estimation for neither the stable boundary layer (SBL) nor the residual layer (RL). Nevertheless, in these decayment and nocturnal phases, the thresholding via the *Rib* synergy does provide an estimation of ABL height that presumably corresponds to the SBL. In order to more accurately assess this, further investigation with reference observations (e.g. radiosondes) is required.

Figure 1: The upper panels show Ri_B diurnal evolution during two summer days (5th of July and 21st of August 2022); negative Ri_B values (unstable ones) are in red and orange, while positive Ri_B (stable) are shown in blue. An estimation of ABL height with $Ri_{bc} = 0.5$ is shown in black contour and the magenta contour shows the higher level reached by convection. The lower panels show the boundary layer classification for the same days, where the convective ABL follows a clear diurnal cycle in red; whereas the blue areas correspond to non-turbulent regions, the yellow ones are intermittent turbulence and the purple stands for in cloud turbulence.

Nevertheless, we noticed that this height is always smaller than the convective height in magenta line. In order to find out what is the role of the thermal part in the Ri_B causing a lower height than the purely dynamic convective height, a detailed analysis of thermal profiles of the MWR and a comparison with radiosonde profiles was performed and is reported in the next section.

Comparison of MWR thermal profiles with radiosonde profiles

The vertical resolution of thermal profiles from the MWR, as well as the sensitivity of the instrument on small changes, directly impacts the ABL height estimation via the Ri_B . To assess these implications, potential temperature profiles from WMR are compared to in situ observations from radiosonde (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Potential temperature profiles from radiosonde (blue) and MWR (red) at 1100 1200 and 1300 UTC on 5th of July (upper panels) and at 1100, 1300 and 1400 UTC on 21st of August (lower panels).

During the first day, i.e., 5th of July, at all the shown times the radiosonde shows a clearly stable layer between 2000 and 2500 m. However, that is not captured by the MWR at the same height, because the positive slope of the MWR retrieved potential temperature starts much lower, at around 1000 m. For the second day: 21st of August, the radiosonde shows two stable layers, one at around 1200 m and the other at around 2000 m. In this case, the stable layer detected by the MWR is very similar to the lower one, at around 1200 m. When comparing this with the ABL heights from *Rib* in figure 1, we notice that for 21st of August this height is also roughly coincident with the convective boundary layer height. On the other hand, the convective height (around 1500 m) is higher than the *Rib* one (~1200 m); but not as high as the radiosonde thermal inversion (~2200 m). From this situation it appears that the ABL height derived from *Rib* is mostly reliable when it is below 1500 m. Therefore, for the summer ABL over Jülich, that frequently exceeds this height, the synergistic *Rib* may not be a suitable technique to provide an ABL height product. Nevertheless, other conditions in which the ABL does not reach these high elevations may be more suitable for being investigated through this synergy, for instance, wintertime and nighttime ABL are usually hardly resolved by only dynamical measurements but could be better understood with a synergistic product like *Rib*. Furthermore, the present synergy analysis reveals that the added value of the *Rib* from MWR and DWL synergy lies in the continuous characterisation of atmospheric stratification in the ABL. As *Rib* considers both thermal and dynamic effects, it can be investigated which is the dominant driver of the atmospheric stability.

Thermal part vs dynamic part in driving instability

Despite the fact that the vertical resolution of Rib (and the sensitivity of the MWR which data we use) are not high enough to provide an ABL height above 1500 m, its temporal resolution does elucidate a detailed evolution of stability in the ABL. Furthermore, the fact that Rib provides a continuous diurnal cycle of instability in the ABL brings in the question of what part is driving the instability: the dynamic or the thermal part. With this in mind, we plotted the two elements in the ratio that constitutes the Rib , and also the potential temperature alone. This is shown for the same two days (5th of July and 21st of August) in figure 3.

The upper plots in figure 3 correspond to the potential temperature, showing a stable stratification with colder potential temperatures closer to the ground and warmer ones at higher levels. During diurnal hours this stable stratification becomes weaker due to thermals and convective mixing. However, the mostly stable stratification is to be expected, because this is the normal stratified profile of the atmosphere. The weaker thermal stratification is observed in daytime hours, which is also a normal behaviour of the ABL, because it starts warming from the ground and this results in rising thermals that erode the thermal stratification. The middle panels of figure 3 show the difference of potential temperature from the first MWR measured level to each height, multiplied by $\frac{gz}{\theta_s}$, just as it is needed for the Rib estimation (equation 1). In the present study we utilised this first level measured by the MWR where the instrument is located, this could lead to unreliable measurements but that doesn't seem to be the case in our resulting variables; however, further comparison with a meteorological station and its temperature measurements are planned to be done in future work. In the middle panels of figure 3, negative values are visible during daytime hours, already elucidating a clear diurnal cycle for both days. Finally, the lower panels show the magnitude of horizontal velocities from DWL, i.e. $u^2 + v^2$. It can be seen that higher horizontal velocities are present in the entrainment zone during the morning growth phase on the 21st of August. However, these velocities do not show a clear diurnal cycle. We also notice a difference in evening conditions after sunset when comparing both days, with higher horizontal velocities on the 5th of July.

Figure 3: Potential temperature (upper panel) difference of potential temperature (middle) and magnitude of horizontal velocities (lower) for 5th of July (left) and 21st of August (right) 2022.

Given that the diurnal cycle is clearly visible from the thermal part (middle panels in figure 3) and not from the horizontal velocities (lower panels), it appears that the diurnal cycle behaviour of Rib in figure 1 is more due to the thermal than the dynamic part. Moreover, from equation 1 we notice that the only way to get negative (unstable) Rib values is if the potential temperature at the ground is higher than the potential temperature at higher levels. However, the magnitude of the horizontal velocity has a role in intensifying or damping the instability. In order to better understand the relative roles of these two components in Rib , we present figure 4. For typical $\frac{gz}{\theta_s}(\theta_z - \theta_s)$ and $u^2 + v^2$ values in figure 3, the Rib is plotted in orange tones for $Rib < 0$ (unstable) and in blue tones for $Rib > 0$ (stable conditions) in figure 4. Given that the typical thresholds for unstable conditions of Rib go from 0.25 to 0.5, neutral conditions were considered in this range and plotted in grey. Figure 4 shows that unstable conditions are always met if $(\theta_z - \theta_s) < 0$; stronger horizontal wind tends to reduce vertical buoyancy through the effect of wind shear. For slightly positive temperature gradients again, it is the horizontal velocities that determine the dynamic atmospheric stability. Only for small $u^2 + v^2$, the stratification is stable while stronger flow dynamics are able to overcome the weak thermal stratification so that in total, the atmosphere remains unstable. Then again if temperature gradients are strongly positive, mechanical turbulence is suppressed and loses importance for the overall assessment of the atmospheric stability.

This analysis helps us to understand how measurement uncertainties and limitations impact the Rib results. The thermal stratification obtained from MWR data is the main driver of the indicator, so that an uncertainty specifically in the first level air temperature has a significant impact on the Rib results. Adding

information on wind shear and mechanical turbulence, is specifically an added value when thermal stratification is near-neutral.

Figure 4: Rib as calculated as a ratio between thermal buoyancy $\frac{gz}{\theta_s} (\theta_z - \theta_s) z$ (y-axis) and mechanical turbulence approximated by $u^2 + v^2$ (x-axis).

Evaluating the shape of the vertical profile of Rib

From examining the Rib diurnal cycle in figure 1, another interesting feature about its structure can be found: darker red colours, i.e. smaller Rib values that indicate the most unstable conditions are not met near the surface but at a certain height within the ABL above around 500 m. In order to more closely examine this behaviour, in the present section Rib profiles are analysed. Additionally, it is important to consider the difference between the Rib profile obtained by radiosonde measurements and the one performed via the synergy MWR-DWL. With this objective we present figure 5, in which both profiles are shown at different times during the same two days (5th of July and 21st of August 2022).

From figure 5, we notice that the Rib from the radiosonde has a higher variability in its structure, which is directly related to the higher vertical resolution that it has. Moreover, it is also clearly visible from these plots that the $Rib = 0.5$ is met at a higher elevation for the Rib in the radiosonde compared with the synergistic Rib ; which also explains the smaller in ABL height estimation via Rib from the synergy. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note that both profiles have a complex shape in which the more negative (unstable) values are reached at a height not immediately above the ground. The radiosonde profile's more complicated structure reveals the existence of multiple minima that are not visible with the synergy. However the synergistic Rib also shows some structure, meeting a minimum value that varies with the time of the day but typically above 200 m and until almost 1000 m on 5th of July and around 800 m on August 21st. This feature

shows an added value that the synergistic Ri_B has, given that, even if the complex structure is not fully captured, the synergy does show that very unstable ABL levels are met not so close to the ground. Another noticeable fact of the radiosonde profiles in Figure 5 is that extremely negative Ri_B values are reached close from the ground; this might be due to some noise in the lower measurements, however it needs to be further investigated and this was not carefully assessed in the present VMG.

This provides a suitable starting point for a long-term investigation about the structure of the instability in the ABL with highly temporally resolved products.

Figure 5: Ri_B profiles for radiosonde (blue) and synergistic product (red).

In order to investigate the structure of the Ri_B profiles also considering the effect of both the thermal and dynamic parts, we present figure 6. For the same radiosonde times in both investigated days, we present the profiles of $\frac{gz}{\theta_s}(\theta_z - \theta_s)$ in brown (from MWR) and of $u^2 + v^2$ in green (from WDL). The brown profile goes from zero to negative values on the levels closer to the ground, and for instance on the 5th of July at 1100 UTC it becomes positive at 1 km, which means that it is there that it changes from unstable to stable conditions thermallywise. The green profile at that same time shows a noticeable horizontal velocity increase at around 1.2 km, which suggests that higher horizontal velocities above the ABL are reached. However, in order to dynamically assess the instability, other more related to turbulence quantities result more useful, as it is further investigated in the next subsection. During other times in figure 6 we notice that a similar behaviour (from negative to positive values as height increases) is detected for the thermal difference profiles and more complex shapes are found for the horizontal velocity profiles. In some cases (2022.07.05 at 1200 UTC and

2022.08.21 at 1100 UTC) a similar structure as the previously pointed out is found, in which higher horizontal velocities are reached presumably above ABL height. Nevertheless, the rest of the times present more complex profiles in which one or more horizontal velocity maxima are reached within the ABL, showing a complex velocity structure inside this layer that is likely to contribute to the instability of it.

Figure 6: Profiles of $\frac{gz}{\theta_s}(\theta_z - \theta_s)$ from MWR (brown) and $u^2 + v^2$ from DWL (green) are shown at the same radiosonde times for the 5th of July and the 21st of August 2022.

In order to exploit the fact that the synergistic *Rib* provides temporally-resolved ABL evolution, we present figure 7, in which synergistic *Rib* profiles are shown also at 0900, 1200, 1500 and 1800 UTC. The earlier *Rib* profile at 0900 UTC (blue) shows a misleading behaviour on the 5th of July and a clear minimum with increasing values with height on the 21st of August. The next *Rib* profiles at 1200 and 1500 UTC (red and yellow) show a complex structure for both days reaching one (on the 5th of July) and two (on the 21st of August) minimums below 1 km, and in negative values, i.e. within the ABL. The later *Rib* profile (purple) shows a less complex structure for both days, reaching values not so drastically negative as earlier profiles; this suggests a less complex ABL stability in the decaying phase, when convective motions don't have an important role anymore. Although these *Rib* profiles do not capture the more complex structures of radiosonde ones (figure 5), they still capture some interesting ABL features and their evolution during daytime, elucidating the capabilities of the *Rib* synergy.

Figure 7: Synergistic *Rib* profiles at 0900 (blue), 1200 (red), 1500 (yellow) and 1800 (purple) UTC on the 5th of July (left) and 21st of August (right) 2022.

Comparison with turbulence quantities: profiles

In order to further assess the influence of turbulent quantities in the complex *Rib* profile structure, we show figure 8. In the first panel, both radiosonde and MWR θ profiles are shown to keep in mind the thermal structure; whereas both radiosonde and synergistically obtained *Rib* profiles are shown in the next panel. Finally, dissipation rate is plotted twice in black in the last two panels in order to diagnose its structure at different scales. In this case we only show profiles for August 21st at 1100 UTC. This case was chosen because the radiosonde *Rib* profile does have a complex structure reaching 2 minimums within the ABL. A situation with only one minimum but still with some structure is revealed by the synergistic *Rib* profile. None of those features seem to be resolved in the thermal structure, not even by the radiosonde θ profile, which suggests that the vertical fluctuations are more related to dynamic quantities. However, the corresponding $u^2 + v^2$ in figure 6 shows that horizontal velocities in the ABL are smaller than above of it. Therefore this constitutes an interesting case to investigate with other dynamical features, in particular with the dissipation rate that is more related to turbulence (Manninen et al. 2018). In the broader picture of this ϵ (panel 3) it is shown that small quite constantly zero values prevail in the first 1.2 km closer to the ground. Whereas the last panel showing a zoom into ϵ shows a more complex structure in these closer to the ground levels. ϵ reaches 3 minimums in this range, however, none of them appears to be at the same height of the θ profile from radiosonde in the second panel. Nevertheless, ϵ also shows a maximum at around 800 m, which is probably related with a minimum at the same height in the θ radiosonde profile. Further investigations relating the *Rib* synergy with turbulent quantities are still encouraged to be performed, however, the present VMG builds into the capabilities and limitations of this valuable synergy.

Figure 8: the two panels of the left show radiosonde (blue) and MWR (red) potential temperature and Ri_B profiles respectively. The two panels on the right they both show the dissipation rate profile, the difference is that on the last panel a zoom has been made in order to further visualize the details on the structure of epsilon in the lower levels.

Conclusions

In the present study the capabilities and limitations of a synergistically obtained Ri_B were assessed using a combination of temperature profile observations from WMR and horizontal wind profile observations from a Doppler wind lidar. In the first place, the obtained ABL height was investigated and the influence of the coarse MWR vertical resolution was analysed. In order to investigate how this coarse resolution and the instrument's sensitivity affect the synergistic Ri_B , profiles of theta and Ri_B were compared with radiosonde ones at three different times during the diurnal evolution of two summer days in JOYCE. It was found that, under these conditions in which the ABL height frequently reaches more than 1.5 km, the MWR tends to identify the thermally stable layer lower than it actually is; which has a direct impact on the Ri_B profile that reaches the threshold and therefore estimates the ABL height at a lower elevation than the radiosonde Ri_B profile. Because of this, in the present VMG we suggest that synergistically obtained Ri_B method can only be utilised to estimate an ABL height if the thermally stable layer is below 1.5 or maybe even lower at around 1.2 km. However, the strength of the inversion may also have an impact on this elevation and it was not explicitly investigated in the present study.

Despite the fact that the present VMG suggests important restrictions on the utilisation of synergistically Ri_B as a method to accurately estimate ABL height, we also show important capabilities that the present synergy provides for a better characterization of ABL. A first important capability relies in the fact that the temporal evolution of MWR, DWL and therefore of Ri_B is good enough to investigate hourly variability and elucidate some interesting features. For instance, when comparing with the convective ABL height in the afternoon decayment, the contemplation of thermal information in the Ri_B provides a smoother decayment of the ABL instability than in the strictly convectively driven height. This is related to thermal inertia and shows how unstable layers are not immediately restricted to their relation with convective motions. Moreover, the fact that turbulence quantities such as ϵ are instantaneously estimated, making them sensitive to smaller features shortly temporally occurring in the ABL and that may not have a decisive influence on the main state of the ABL. Variables that also include thermal information are less sensitive to these perturbations and therefore are valuable to understand the temporal evolution of the main features in the ABL.

Furthermore, the inclusion of thermal information is capable of providing some height up to which instability reaches at nighttime, providing a presumably stable layer height in some cases (e.g. at 20000 UTC on the 21st of August 2022, see figure 1).

The employment of *Rib* synergy that has both thermal and dynamical information also allows us to investigate whether the instability is being driven by the thermal or the dynamic part. In the present VMG we illustrate that the diurnal cycle in the instability is mostly being driven by the thermal part (figure 3). However, it is the dynamic part that was found to be responsible for the complex structure on the *Rib* profiles (figure 6). Furthermore, the estimation of *Rib* synergistically at times when there is no radiosonde, also allow us to investigate the evolution of the complex structures of this profile as the diurnal cycle evolves. As figure 7 shows, *Rib* profiles with sharper minimums within the ABL are present in diurnal convective hours, while a smoother *Rib* profile results at 1800, when the afternoon decayment has already been reached. Finally, the complex shapes of both radiosonde and synergistic *Rib* profiles aimed to also be investigated when comparing them to turbulence quantities profiles. In the present VMG we only did that with the ϵ , which indicates the presence of turbulence. Although not conclusive feature could be derived from figure 8, the present VMG provides a starting point for better investigating the relationship between *Rib* profile and turbulence quantities, which is aimed to be explored in future work.

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